

THIRTY-SIXTH ANNUAL REPORT 1992

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-SIXTH ANNUAL REPORT 1992

*1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Suite 313
Washington, D.C. 20036*

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine...* Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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Members of the Board of Directors*

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W. David Penniman
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Emory University*

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Former President, Upjohn Company

Basil Stuart-Stubbs
*Former Director, School of Library, Archival and
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Sidney Verba
Director, Harvard University Library

Robert Vosper ¹
*University Librarian Emeritus
University of California, Los Angeles*

Frederick H. Wagman ²
*Professor Emeritus, School of Information and
Library Studies
University of Michigan*

1. Retired, May 1992.
2. Retired, November 1991.

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Robert Vosper
Frederick H. Wagman
Herman B Wells

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Charles D. Churchwell
W. David Penniman
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James S. Coles
Caryl P. Haskins ³
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Charles D. Churchwell, Vice Chairman
W. David Penniman, President
Mary Agnes Thompson, Secretary and Treasurer

1. Retired, May 1992.
2. Retired, November 1991.
3. Elected at the November 1991 Directors' meeting.
4. Until November 1991.

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Julia C. Blixrud, Program Officer ⁵
Martin M. Cummings, Consultant
Vanessa K. Lee, Administrative Assistant
Suzette M. Lemrow, Secretary ⁵
Albert C. McIlwain II, Administrative Assistant ⁶
Caroline A. Mitchell, Program Associate ⁷
W. David Penniman, President
Henry W. Riecken, Consultant
Mary Agnes Thompson, Assistant to the President;
Secretary and Treasurer
Ellen B. Timmer, Administrative Assistant

5. As of December 1991.

6. Retired, November 1991.

7. Resigned, October 1991.

Acknowledgements

The following foundations were among the supporters of Council activities during 1991/1992. All deserve the thanks of the library community.

AT&T Foundation

Engineering Foundation

The J. Paul Getty Trust

The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation

The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation

National Science Foundation

Chairman's Message

When the Council on Library Resources was created over thirty-five years ago, its purpose was stated in a deceptively simple form: "to aid in the solution of library problems." Today, "library problems" such as shrinking budgets and rising costs are a subset of larger societal problems, and the institutions that libraries serve (e.g., universities, communities, schools, government agencies, and corporations) are facing economic and sociopolitical challenges of an unprecedented nature. Traditional foundation funding sources for library programs and research have turned to broader societal issues of poverty, urban decay, racial discrimination, failing educational systems, and deteriorating infrastructure, as well as international challenges.

For the library of today to be part of the solution rather than just another institution in need, we must support programs that demonstrate the relevance of libraries to the problems of today and tomorrow. It is not enough to cast libraries in the role of preservers of knowledge. Libraries, and particularly librarians, must be active agents in the problem-solving process and promote the idea that the knowledge they preserve is useful in that process. Issues of access, staffing, and collection development are important when the library itself is seen as a vital link in providing information that may be used to solve new challenges. The Council is anxious to strengthen that linkage.

Maximilian W. Kempner
Chairman

President's Message

As I look back over my first full year as president of the Council, I am pleased with a number of the accomplishments covered in this annual report. One change not mentioned elsewhere in this report was initiated by the Board of Directors to assure its own continuous rejuvenation. Effective with all newly elected members, terms will be limited to three years. Members may be elected to a maximum of three successive terms, for a total of nine years. New Board members will be sought from a variety of sources and with a variety of backgrounds.

The Council has articulated a new set of programs, and the projects and activities already under way have been incorporated into these program areas. The four program areas—human resources, economics, infrastructure, and access/processing—will create the framework for the future direction of the Council. Our chairman, Maximilian Kempner, has articulated our challenge in his message. We must “support programs that demonstrate the relevance of libraries to the problems of today and tomorrow.” We, in turn, must gain support from a wider range of foundations by demonstrating that libraries are relevant to the issues foundations now address.

During this past year we had broad-based support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation for our new programs. The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation provided specific support for our newly defined economics and access/processing programs, and the AT&T Foundation supported a project in the infrastructure area. Several other projects in the infrastructure area continued to be funded by a grant from the J. Paul Getty Trust. In addition, the Engineering Foundation and the National Science Foundation helped support a major conference the Council helped conduct on using networks to improve the engineering information environment.

The Council this year provided support for a grass-roots effort involving librarians from all sectors to articulate a vision for librarianship in the next century. This vision, described in more detail in the human

resources section of the program review, is meant to help demonstrate the vital role librarianship plays in society. There is still much to do, obviously, in demonstrating to foundations and other communities that libraries are vitally related to the broader societal issues of interest to them. In my view, meeting that challenge is the primary goal of the Council for the coming year.

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "W. David Penniman". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style with a large initial "W".

W. David Penniman
President

Program Review

During the early part of his tenure, CLR president David Penniman met with representatives of a variety of institutions: library school deans, university library directors, faculty and staff, university senior administrators, professional organizations, public and special librarians, and other information professionals. In wide-ranging discussions he learned about their concerns and aspirations regarding the future of libraries as well as their parent institutions. After considering the issues raised in these and other discussions, along with the current library and information science environment, the Council developed a set of four program areas in which it will focus its attention and resources over the next several years. These categories—human resources, economics, infrastructure, and access/processing—provide a framework for addressing a wide range of projects in the library and information science arena. Some projects and grants under way this year are described below.

Human Resources

Advances in the areas of access and processing, economics, or infrastructure would be pointless unless competent and imaginative leaders are prepared to implement those advances. The Council's human resources program is intended to help develop leaders who can build and manage the information support systems needed by society and to assist current leaders in developing the skills needed to transform their institutions in response to changing societal needs.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

The Academic Library Management Intern Program, established in 1974, continues to be both useful and successful. It is offered biennially for librarians who have an interest in the administration of large libraries and who wish to improve their management skills. Fourteen classes of interns have been selected since the program

began. Applications come from individuals with high professional aspirations; the internships provide them with an exceptional opportunity for personal development. The interns are chosen by a selection committee that considers factors such as experience, administrative abilities, education, personal references, and the content of a statement required from each applicant.

Interns spend the academic year working with the director and senior administrative staff of a large and well-managed research library. Thus, an important component of the program is the willingness of the directors and staffs of such libraries to host the chosen interns. While the individual programs vary, all interns observe and participate in management activities and undertake special assignments. The goal of the program is to expose the interns to the complexity of a wide array of policy matters and the operations of large research libraries.

Heather Gordon, Director of Information Services, Alberta Department of Labour, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada, and Judy McQueen, library consultant, Chicago, Illinois, were selected as the members of the CLR Academic Library Management Intern Program class of 1992/93. Gordon will serve her internship at Duke University with Jerry D. Campbell, University Librarian. McQueen will intern with Richard De Gennaro, Roy E. Larsen Librarian of Harvard College at Harvard University.

The selection committee for the 1992/93 intern program included educators, library directors, and former interns. (See page 28 for a list of committee members.) The selection process began with an independent review and evaluative ranking of the applications by each member of the committee. The full committee met at CLR to discuss their evaluations and decided on the candidates to be interviewed. Candidates were invited to Washington for an interview with the selection committee and CLR staff. Upon completion of the interviews, the committee then recommended individuals to the CLR president to be awarded internships.

A description of the intern program appears in "CLR Academic Library Management Intern Program," by Caroline A. Mitchell, former CLR program associate, which was published in the Winter 1992 issue of *Library Administration & Management*.

Strategic Visions

The Strategic Visions Discussion Group, formed by a group of librarians interested in the role of the librarian and the library of the future, received support from the Council during 1991/92. A Steering Committee meeting was held at Georgetown University in December 1991, and a subsequent meeting was held at the Palmer School of Library and Information Studies, Long Island University, in May 1992.

The Strategic Visions Steering Committee generated a draft vision statement that is being circulated widely. The document identifies four areas of librarianship on which to focus attention: service, leadership, innovation, and recruitment/development. Under these categories, the committee describes actions that delineate the characteristics of the librarian in the twenty-first century.

In addition, the committee generated a discussion draft of the values and qualities of librarianship desired in the next century. While the committee agreed that a values statement is desirable, it is the most difficult task for the group to resolve. Several issues have emerged as needing further discussion:

Issue 1. The distinction between the values of libraries as institutions and the values of librarians as professionals is not easy to make.

Issue 2. The qualities desirable for librarians in the future were observed to be not only obvious, but not necessarily unique to librarianship; they are qualities applicable for all professions.

Issue 3. While this issue has not been discussed in depth, it is certainly necessary that library schools and libraries recruit to the profession people who have the qualities and share the values appropriate for librarians in the twenty-first century.

Other visions discussions were held at several professional meetings, with hundreds of interested people attending each session. In addition to meeting discussions, brief articles about the visions effort are now appearing in the library literature. The Visions Listserv, partially supported by CLR, has over 250 subscribers and offers an opportunity for individuals to post and discuss their views of the future library and librarian. To subscribe, send a message to listserv@library.sdsu.edu. Copies of the draft vision and values documents are available from the Council.

The need for useful economic data continues to be expressed by the library community and the institutions it serves. The Council's economics program will support projects that focus attention on the costs and benefits of specific library services and that lead to more systematic decision making regarding allocation of funding and cost sharing. Support for Council activities in the program area of economics has come from the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation.

- During the summer of 1991, the Council convened a Study Group on the Microeconomics of Library Operations. Members of the study group are listed on page 29. The study group identified several areas of interest in the economics area, including document delivery, public service costs, choice of formats for providing information (online, CD-ROM, etc.), cycle times and total quality management, and performance evaluation of institutions.

- The Council provided partial support for a study of interlibrary loan costs by the Association of Research Libraries and the Research Libraries Group. Results of the study are expected to be published in early 1993.

- Close to two hundred information professionals have attended workshops on "The Quality Imperative," cosponsored by CLR and the Special Libraries Association. Interest in utilizing total quality management or quality service management is high in many libraries and their parent institutions.

- A CLR grant to the Urban Libraries Council supported a seminar examining the results of a study of exemplary public library financial practices, which was conducted for the U.S. Department of Education's Office of Library Programs. The seminar was held in May 1992, and proceedings will be published in 1993.

Infrastructure is an umbrella term for the systems, services, and facilities that are drawn upon to help libraries and other information services operate more efficiently and effectively. Elements covered under this term include buildings, communication networks, bibliographic utilities, software and hardware vendor communities, and publishers. The goal of the Council's infrastructure program is to establish continuing communication and cooperation among the various information systems and services that support libraries and to assure that economic, sociopolitical, technical, and legal changes do not inhibit library functions or access to information by individuals and groups.

Knowledge Management

Support continued for The Johns Hopkins University's Welch Medical Library and its Laboratory for Applied Research in Academic Information, whose mission is the development of knowledge management environments. The goal of knowledge management is the organization and dissemination of scholarly knowledge through the application of computing and communication technologies. A knowledge base may contain all or some part of the intellectual core of a scholarly topic or discipline, and it is constructed through the collaborative efforts of scholars and research librarians.

A considerable portion of the Laboratory's efforts was devoted to transforming a printed volume on human genetics into an electronically stored, regularly updated knowledge base that was accessible to geneticists worldwide. The success of this enterprise led researchers to ask how appropriate a knowledge management model might be for other academic disciplines. This question was explored in a symposium held in October 1991, whose results are summarized in a *Synopsis* that has been published by the Welch Library. The synopsis covers such issues as intellectual property law, financial and technological strategies, institutional infrastructure, and the clarification and elaboration of the knowledge management model.

A National Engineering Information Network

An estimated \$8.3 billion is spent annually in support of information access by engineers.¹ In spite of this sizable investment, the sources of engineering information and data are highly fragmented and dispersed, and there is no efficient route of access to these various sources. This situation inhibits our ability to exploit existing engineering know-how to benefit our educational institutions and industries. Improving access to this valuable resource will yield a significant return on investment and improve our competitive position in the international arena.

The Council on Library Resources and the Engineering Foundation (with supplemental support from the AT&T Foundation and the National Science Foundation) cosponsored a five-day conference in June 1992 to address this issue. Ninety librarians, information scientists, and engineers representing government, industry, professional societies, and universities met to develop a plan to improve access to engineering information in our nation's libraries and specialized information services.

After a number of background presentations, professional facilitators guided the participants through a series of workshops designed to converge on a set of recommendations and an action plan to enhance information access and utilization for engineers. The action plan emerged with three distinct components:

The top-down component involves forming a group of high-level experts to conceptualize and advise on the development of a nationwide network (perhaps building on the National Research and Education Network) of distributed databases and services—in effect, a “virtual library.” Within this network, the current stakeholder enterprises will become active, participating nodes rather than being superseded.

The bottom-up component was popular among many of the participants who are currently involved in providing information services to engineers. These participants expressed their belief that they could begin improving engineering information access by creating links among existing networks and resources and by forming a coalition that communicates regularly and initiates grass-roots pilot projects in cooperation with the experts involved in the top-down component.

¹ See José-Marie Griffiths, “Existing Cost/Benefit Picture,” in *Exploration of a National Engineering Information Service* (Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell Information Technologies, 1992), 407.

The conference also generated five concrete initiatives to be pursued in coordination with the top-down and bottom-up activities. These *more defined* activities will have the following objectives:

- To incorporate into university curricula courses in efficient utilization and exploitation of engineering information and data
- To study the requirements of the users of engineering information and data to provide input to the design considerations of the top-down initiative
- To build coalitions among groups of people with existing related activities
- To encourage participants in the bottom-up activities to conduct self-funded pilot projects
- To *foster electronic network conferencing by participants in the bottom-up activities*

The Council will manage and coordinate the integrated action plan and is actively seeking funding to support the program. The figure shown on the following page illustrates the integrated nature of the action plan components.

Integrated Action Plan for a National Engineering Information Network

Network Advisory Committee

Over the past fifteen years, the Council has provided substantial support to the Network Advisory Committee (NAC). Membership in NAC is composed of U.S. organizations formally constituted and functioning in the public or private (for-profit or not-for-profit) sector that are actively engaged in regional or nationwide networking of library and information services, or have a significant impact on the development of nationwide networks providing library and information services.

The December 1991 meeting of NAC focused on the role of the national libraries in the evolving national network. Shirley Echelman, formerly Executive Director of the Association of Research Libraries, prepared a paper for discussion at the meeting. Final recommendations from that meeting included encouragement to national libraries to continue their leadership role in bibliographic control, standards, and preservation.

The April 1992 meeting addressed the topic of the role of state libraries in the evolving national information network. The meeting was jointly sponsored by NAC and COSLA (Chief Officers of State Library Agencies).

Setting Library Policies and Priorities in Research Universities

This special grant program provided support to four institutions or consortia for studying management and service issues in research libraries and developing strategic plans for dealing with those issues. All four projects are ongoing. The brief accounts that follow should be regarded as progress or interim reports.

Columbia University has completed the data collection phase of studies and surveys of library use and users in three science departments, and has begun analysis of the data. Preliminary findings document distinct differences among users from different disciplines in their use of online information aids, and confirm that library collections of journals in the sciences are much more important for graduate students than for faculty, since faculty depend more on personal collections and use the library's collection for browsing. Some pilot projects are being planned to compare the effectiveness and costs of journal ownership versus document delivery through interlibrary loan. Cost studies will also be extended to questions of pricing policy and cost sharing among the university library, academic

departments, and individual users. Finally, a serendipitous outcome of the project is the opportunity it has to feed information to task forces that are responsible for developing a recently announced university-wide strategic plan.

Harvard University finished a major segment of its project by completing the strategic planning process that involved library staff working with faculty members. The report of the project, *Commitment to Renewal: A Strategic Plan for the Harvard College Library*, is available from the Harvard University Publications Office. The plan includes strategic goals for space and catalog conversion, for collections and access, for library use and services, for new technologies, and for allocation of resources. Work has begun on a second segment, interinstitutional cooperation in collection development and the preservation of materials.

The **SUNY consortium** (the State University of New York campuses at Albany, Binghamton, Buffalo, and Stony Brook) has conducted three major studies to gather background data for the development of library and information services policy. The journal use study gathered data on usage of both current unbound issues and bound backfile volumes over a one-year period. These data are expected to provide information on collection overlap among the four institutions participating, profiles of usage for duplicated titles, an LC class profile of holdings and use patterns, and analysis of variations in usage among institutions. The interlibrary loan study used a sample of one thousand journal article requests from each institution to determine which titles are requested, how well the four libraries can supply these titles, which libraries are actually supplying them, and how long it takes to supply them. The third study focused on faculty need and opinion regarding use of information available over campus and national networks, on current faculty use of materials in electronic form, and on faculty expectations regarding library services in a networked environment. Data analysis is expected to be completed in the spring of 1993.

Triangle Research Libraries Network (Duke University, University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill, and North Carolina State University) has been conducting the studies it had planned: a survey of faculty and graduate students in science and engineering on the three campuses to elicit data on current sources of information both inside and

outside the library; and a statistical profile of the sciences and engineering at the three universities. The profile has been completed, as has the information use survey, which is currently being analyzed.

In addition to these studies, an initiative has been undertaken that was not initially planned, but which emerged from the consortium-wide symposium that initiated project activity in May 1991. A Copyright Issues subcommittee has been meeting to draft a position paper that might, after suitable revision, serve as a model for university policy regarding faculty publication in scholarly journals. The position paper addresses the problems raised by transfer of copyright from author to publisher, which may act as a barrier to the wide sharing of new ideas and research results. Various forms of limited copyright transfer are being explored, and the project is soliciting comment widely in the academic and publishing communities.

Access/Processing

In recent years, changes in information availability, means of delivery, and costs of processing have challenged the traditional processing and access activities of libraries. The purpose of the Council's efforts in this area is to create ongoing mechanisms that encourage improvement in the internal processes performed by libraries so that access to information is enhanced and the resources invested in libraries are used more efficiently and effectively. Put simply, the Council seeks to assist libraries in providing information to their users in an efficient and usable form.

Bibliographic Services Study Committee

The nucleus of activity within the Council's access and processing program area is the Bibliographic Services Study Committee (BSSC). Since 1987, the committee has assisted the Council in identifying programs and projects that would improve and enhance the bibliographic services provided by libraries. During 1991/92, the BSSC continued to advise the Council and focus discussion on the issues of information access and bibliographic processing.

One CLR-supported activity related to BSSC interests was a Subject Subdivisions Conference held in May 1991. The conference was organized by the Library of Congress in response to growing concern that the cataloging process has become unnecessarily complex. The results of the conference, published by the Library of Congress as *The Future of Subdivisions in the Library of Congress Subject Headings System*, were disseminated to the library community during the fall of 1991; the publication consists of sixteen papers that address four proposals for change in subdivision practice.

In the spring of 1992, the BSSC and invited guests met to discuss the future library catalog and its implications for library bibliographic services. The meeting provided an opportunity to address some of the specific concerns raised by new technologies and the online catalog. The BSSC meeting participants discussed why library users are not provided with better catalogs, even though much is known about information retrieval and users' information-seeking behavior. They speculated on the reasons for the stagnation of library cataloging and catalog-building practices as catalogs changed from card to online to "expanded" catalogs. The participants wondered about the reasons libraries are cutting back on cataloging and seeking cost-saving "simplifications" at the same time experts call for enriched and expanded catalog records. They questioned also how processing might contribute most cost-effectively to access.

The library community needs an easily grasped and agreed-upon conceptual structure on which to build new functions, new operations, and common visions for the future online public access catalog (OPAC). The current OPAC concept is too limiting, and the concept of a campus-wide or community information system is too broad.

If the catalog is at the center of an access model, what metaphor best represents that center—a person, a system, a service, a desktop, a workstation? Each metaphor has drawbacks, but a universal window comes closest to the essential concept.

While there are a number of developing information delivery services providing direct access to the end-user, the BSSC meeting participants agreed that libraries will continue to be central delivery systems. The library as "place" and the "virtual library" will also co-exist for some time to come, since it is unlikely that the vast majority of paper-based collections will soon be converted to electronic form.

The library will continue to acquire and provide access to local collections, but its key role will shift to one of assembling and linking records and databases and connecting them to item delivery. Design

of the window, acquisition of databases (both records and indexing information), coordination of machine-based authority processes, and methods of ensuring that records can be acquired and used in the most efficient manner possible will become more and more important responsibilities for librarians of the future.

The BSSC has recommended a combination of research and demonstration projects and professional education efforts to effect change in the functionality of the catalog/window, in the nature of the information available through libraries, and in how libraries provide access to that information in the window. Research and demonstration projects would aid in answering some of the questions on the nature of the catalog record. White papers, seminars, conferences, and other educational programs would help to break conceptual barriers and provide momentum for change.

Subject Access

The Council provided continuing support to a researcher at Indiana University of Pennsylvania to develop an online catalog search system that incorporates unobtrusive aids for subdividing, clustering, and otherwise organizing the retrieval set, as well as suggesting additional or alternative search tactics. The searcher can examine the results of a first pass and then ask that the search be broadened (for example, if only one item—or none at all—has been retrieved) or narrowed (if dozens of books have been found). In either case, the system itself tailors the next search. A method for weighting the items in the retrieved set provides the searcher with what amounts to a list that is rank-ordered by relevance. In addition, the system allows the user to “browse” (by machine) the titles of books that are shelved adjacent to a given item and to scan their tables of contents. Further details are available from the principal investigator, Dr. Mary Micco, at the Computer Science Department of Indiana University of Pennsylvania.

Information Retrieval Systems and Their Users

In 1990 the Council made a grant to two teams of investigators at the universities of Maryland and Toronto to conduct a series of experiments on the interaction between bibliographic information retrieval systems and their users. The investigators expected the results to guide system designers in determining what features of systems might be most effective for various kinds of users.

The experiments compared the search behavior and the results obtained by two types of users: professional librarians/information specialists (“search experts”); and members of a learned profession (“domain experts”). The results suggest that the two groups were searching in quite different ways. Domain specialists seem to have mental models of the answer to a problem, and direct their efforts to matching results to the model. Search experts seem to have mental models for the structure of a database and focus their effort on the system. Search experts, for example, spend much more time formulating their inquiries, while domain experts spend much more time scanning text. Search experts make more use of the formal vocabulary and the system-provided searching techniques, whereas domain experts tend to originate more terms and carry out an associative process of searching that resembles browsing. The two classes of searcher not only have different mental models of the information space they are navigating; they also use different cues and different strategies for proceeding.

These results suggest that vocabulary support, perhaps in the form of expanded thesauri, would be beneficial to search experts. The “browsing” domain experts, on the other hand, might be better served by system features that help them to assess the reasonableness of retrieved sets and to display text rapidly— e.g., highlighting terms and showing links from term to term.

Committees

Academic Library Management Intern Program Selection Committee

Charles D. Churchwell (Chair)
Clark Atlanta University
Joan Chambers
Colorado State University
Deanna Marcum
The Catholic University of America
Sarah Pritchard
Association of Research Libraries
Martin Runkle
University of Chicago
Elliott Shelkrot
Free Library of Philadelphia

Bibliographic Services Study Committee

Carol Mandel (Chair)
Columbia University
Dorothy Gregor
University of California, Berkeley
Martin Runkle
University of Chicago

Proposal Review Committee, 1991/92

Deanna Marcum (Chair)
The Catholic University of America
David Bishop
University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign
Martin Cummings
Council on Library Resources
Nina Matheson
The Johns Hopkins University
Warren Seibert
National Library of Medicine (retired)

Study Group on the Microeconomics of Library Operations

Malcolm Getz (Chair)

Vanderbilt University

Larry Besant

Morehead State University

Martin Cummings

Council on Library Resources

Miriam Drake

Georgia Institute of Technology

Paul Kantor

Rutgers University

W. David Penniman

Council on Library Resources

Catherine Quinlan

University of Western Ontario

Publications and Reports Resulting from CLR Programs, 1991/1992

Part I. Publications of the Council and CLR Staff ■

Blixrud, Julia C. "The International Serials Data System (ISDS)." In *Managing the Preservation of Serial Literature: An International Symposium*, edited by Merrily A. Smith, 146-50. Paper presented at a conference held at the Library of Congress, Washington, D.C., May 22-24, 1989. IFLA Publications 57. Munich: K.G. Saur, 1992.

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Richardson, John, Jr. "The Logic of Ready Reference Work: Basic and Subordinate Level Knowledge." In *Libraries and Expert Systems*, Proceedings of a conference and workshop held at Charles Sturt University, Riverina, Australia, July 1990, edited by Craig McDonald and John Weckert, 7-16. London: Taylor Graham, 1991.

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Part III. Project Reports Received

Many project reports are published in the professional literature. Authors retain ownership of the reports and are asked to submit copies to the ERIC database. ERIC document numbers that have been reported to CLR are listed at the end of the citation. Inquiries about reports without an ERIC number should be addressed to the author.

"Commitment to Renewal: A Strategic Plan for the Harvard College Library." Harvard University, February 1992.

Ferl, Terry Ellen, and Larry Millsap. "Remote Use of the University of California MELVYL Library System." University of California, Santa Cruz, January 1992.

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Gyeszly, Suzanne D., and Jane A. Dodd. "Automated Collection Analysis and Development: Business Collection." Texas A & M University, May 1992.

Havener, W. Michael, Wilbur A. Stolt, and Robert Swisher. "Career and Communication Patterns of Academic Librarians: A State Level Study." University of Oklahoma, September 1991.

Hewitt, Joe A. "The Process of Organizational Review in Research Libraries." University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, July 1991.

Meadow, Charles T., Jiabin Wang, and Weijing Yuan. "A Comparison of User Performance with Different Information Retrieval Interfaces: Final Program Report." University of Toronto, April 1992.

Rappa, Michael A., and Raghu Garud. "Using the Literature in the Study of Emerging Fields of Science and Technology: An Examination of Researcher Contribution Spans." Massachusetts Institute of Technology, July 1991.

Richardson, John, Jr. "The Elucidation and Validation of the Knowledge Used by Reference Librarians in the Decision-Making Process of Answering Reference Questions." University of California, Los Angeles, December 1991.

Stewart, Linda. "End Use of Bibliographic Databases Accessible through the Campus Network." Cornell University, July 1991.

Svenonius, Elaine, and Dorothy McGarry. "Objectivity in Evaluating Subject Heading Assignment." University of California, Los Angeles, June 1992.

Thomas, Sarah E. "CatTutor: Final Report to the Council on Library Resources." National Agricultural Library, September 1991.

Tiefel, Virginia. "Examining Innovative Applications of Technology in Libraries." Ohio State University, January 1992.

Woodsworth, Anne, et al. "The Information Job Family: An Examination of the Effects of Integrating Information Technologies on Job Classification and Compensation Systems." Long Island University, May 1992.

Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad areas of the Council's program, as described in this report: human resources, the economics of information services, infrastructure, and access and processing.

In addition, the Council sponsors several competitive programs, including the CLR Fellows program, the Cooperative Research program, and the Academic Library Management Intern Program. These programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested.

Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including objectives and methods to be employed. A timetable, pertinent background information, and plans for evaluation of results should also be provided.
3. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and, when necessary, external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and

importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. With the exception of a few cyclical programs, there are no submission deadlines.

Support is not provided for construction or renovation, collection acquisitions, routine operating costs, activities judged to be of limited influence, or work that essentially repeats previous research. CLR does not fund indirect costs or, with rare exceptions, equipment purchases. While CLR, in consultation with its advisors, often initiates and promotes work in program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

All inquiries should be addressed to Julia C. Blixrud, Program Officer, Council on Library Resources, 1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Suite 313, Washington, D.C. 20036.

***Active Projects
Financial Statements***

Grants and Contracts Active
in Fiscal 1992 (unaudited)

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>American Association of Engineering Societies</i> <i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Planning a thesaurus of engineering and scientific terms	-0-	19,500	9,750	9,750
<i>American Council of Learned Societies</i> <i>New York, N.Y.</i>				
Implications of electronic information resources	-0-	10,000	10,000	-0-
<i>American Library Association</i> <i>Chicago, Ill.</i>				
Preconference on reference effectiveness	-0-	1,200	1,200	-0-
Standards for ethical conduct for rare book, manuscript, and special collections librarians	5,000	-0-	3,200	1,800
<i>Association of Research Libraries</i> <i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Interlibrary loan cost study	-0-	10,000	8,000	2,000
<i>Marcia Bates</i> <i>Van Nuys, Calif.</i>				
Examine the possibility of expanded entry vocabulary for Library of Congress subject headings	-0-	6,000	-0-	6,000
<i>The Bridge to China Foundation</i> <i>Oakland, Calif.</i>				
National publicity for an American book drive for Asia	-0-	1,500	1,500	-0-
<i>California State University</i> <i>Chico, Calif.</i>				
Packet radio Internet extension	-0-	9,048	8,000	1,048
<i>Columbia University</i> <i>New York, N.Y.</i>				
Recasting scientific information delivery	50,000	-0-	-0-	50,000

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>Commission on Preservation and Access</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
General support	66,667	-0-	66,667	-0-
<i>Conservation Center for Art and Historic Artifacts</i>				
<i>Philadelphia, Pa.</i>				
Research on the preservation and fabrication of American architectural drawings to 1930	-0-	8,916	7,000	1,916
<i>Cornell University</i>				
<i>Geneva, N.Y.</i>				
Core literature research in horticulture, 1850-1950	500	(3)	497	-0-
<i>Earlham College</i>				
<i>Richmond, Ind.</i>				
Determining factors leading Earlham College graduates to enter library schools	-0-	1,000	-0-	1,000
<i>Eckerd College</i>				
<i>St. Petersburg, Fla.</i>				
College library director mentor program	-0-	24,000	8,000	16,000
<i>Franklin & Marshall College</i>				
<i>Lancaster, Pa.</i>				
Preservation and collection manage- ment at liberal arts college libraries	480	(940)	(460)	-0-
<i>Georgetown University</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Explore issues related to the role of the librarian and the library of the future	-0-	15,500	15,500	-0-
Support for the Strategic Visions Steering Committee	-0-	20,000	15,000	5,000
<i>Harvard University</i>				
<i>Cambridge, Mass.</i>				
Strategic planning process	50,000	-0-	-0-	50,000

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>Charles R. Hildreth</i>				
<i>Springfield, Ill.</i>				
Study of functionality of online catalogs	-0-	11,000	-0-	11,000
<i>International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions</i>				
<i>The Hague, Netherlands</i>				
IFLA Fellows program	40,000	-0-	-0-	40,000
<i>Japan Information Access Project</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Symposium on access to, use of, and demand for Japanese information	-0-	5,000	4,500	500
<i>Johns Hopkins University</i>				
<i>Baltimore, Md.</i>				
Knowledge management: expanding the scholarly role of research libraries	132,808	(55,517)	54,394	22,897
<i>Library of Congress</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
East European bibliographies and European networks conference	-0-	9,875	9,000	875
<i>Long Island University</i>				
<i>Brookville, N.Y.</i>				
Complete study of the effects of integrating information technologies on job classification and compensation systems	-0-	11,855	8,000	3,855
<i>Mississippi State University</i>				
<i>Mississippi State, Miss.</i>				
Analysis of price discrimination of economics journals	-0-	3,109	3,109	-0-
<i>National Agricultural Library</i>				
<i>Beltsville, Md.</i>				
Development of a computer-assisted instructional program for cataloging	5,084	-0-	5,084	-0-

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>National Information Standards Organization Bethesda, Md.</i>				
Development of technical standards for the preservation of library materials	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
<i>Northwestern University Evanston, Ill.</i>				
Prototype workstation for user access to other libraries	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
<i>Oberlin College Oberlin, Ohio</i>				
Survey of undergraduate science library facilities	-0-	1,258	1,258	-0-
<i>Maxine H. Reneker Palo Alto, Calif.</i>				
Information seeking among mem- bers of an academic community	500	-0-	-0-	500
<i>Rutgers University New Brunswick, N.J.</i>				
Creation of a preliminary music thesaurus	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-
<i>SKP Associates New York, N.Y.</i>				
Evaluation of the Cataloging in Publication Program	12,500	-0-	-0-	12,500
<i>San Diego State University San Diego, Calif.</i>				
Listserv operations for Strategic Visions Group	-0-	1,200	1,200	-0-
<i>Simmons College Boston, Mass.</i>				
Study of the decision-making process for collection development in libraries	-0-	6,359	5,500	859
<i>Southern Illinois University Carbondale, Ill.</i>				
International directory of children's literature	599	(524)	75	-0-

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>Special Libraries Association</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Development of continuing education course on total quality management	-0-	12,000	6,000	6,000
<i>State University of New York</i>				
<i>Buffalo, N.Y.</i>				
Cooperative Planning Grant	50,000	-0-	-0-	50,000
<i>Texas A & M University</i>				
<i>College Station, Tex.</i>				
Automated collection analysis and development in a business collection	2,245	-0-	2,245	-0-
<i>University of Alabama</i>				
<i>Tuscaloosa, Ala.</i>				
Book on library education	2,300	-0-	2,300	-0-
<i>University of Arizona</i>				
<i>Tucson, Ariz.</i>				
Study of the effectiveness of affirmative action guidelines on the recruitment and promotion of minority librarians	-0-	2,879	2,879	-0-
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Berkeley, Calif.</i>				
The Humanist and the Library	4,000	-0-	4,000	-0-
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Los Angeles, Calif.</i>				
Elucidation and validation of the knowledge used by reference librarians	1,330	-0-	-0-	1,330
Technology and structure of research libraries	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Riverside, Calif.</i>				
European Short Title Catalogue	-0-	24,500	8,000	16,500
Meeting on standardization of bibliographic form and genre terminology	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>University of Chicago</i>				
<i>Chicago, Ill.</i>				
Study of book borrowing from the Harvard College Library, 1773-1800	-0-	4,420	4,420	-0-
<i>University of Colorado</i>				
<i>Boulder, Colo.</i>				
Distributing responsibilities for accessing and indexing polar regions information	-0-	15,190	-0-	15,190
<i>University of Illinois</i>				
<i>Chicago, Ill.</i>				
Users' persistence in scanning postings in an online public access catalog	-0-	5,330	4,000	1,330
<i>University of Illinois</i>				
<i>Urbana, Ill.</i>				
Advancing research on the library in transition	6,786	-0-	6,786	-0-
A history of Argentina's National Library under the directorship of Hugo Wast, 1931-1955	500	-0-	-0-	500
Study of searching strategies on CD-ROM	2,512	-0-	-0-	2,512
Workshops on library applications of data processing	-0-	3,440	3,440	-0-
<i>University of Nebraska</i>				
<i>Lincoln, Nebr.</i>				
Reliability study of conspectus methodology	-0-	3,200	3,200	-0-
<i>University of North Carolina</i>				
<i>Chapel Hill, N.C.</i>				
Cooperative information resources development	50,000	-0-	-0-	50,000
End user searching of MEDLINE	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-

	FY 1992			
	Unpaid 6/30/91	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/92
<i>University of Pittsburgh</i>				
<i>Pittsburgh, Pa.</i>				
Examination of the effects of integrating information technologies on job classification and compensa- tion systems	1,560	(11,855)	(11,855)	1,560
<i>University of Rhode Island</i>				
<i>Kingston, R.I.</i>				
Study of replacement needs for library school faculty	850	(850)	-0-	-0-
<i>University of South Carolina</i>				
<i>Columbia, S.C.</i>				
Study of the knowledge and skills required for health information professionals	4,830	(3,214)	-0-	1,616
<i>University of Toronto</i>				
<i>Toronto, Ontario, Canada</i>				
Information retrieval systems and their users	5,000	-0-	5,000	-0-
<i>Urban Libraries Council</i>				
<i>State College, Pa.</i>				
Seminar on successful public library financial practices	-0-	5,000	4,500	500
<i>Yale University</i>				
<i>New Haven, Conn.</i>				
Instant mathematics preprint project	1,500	-0-	-0-	1,500
<i>Current year adjustments; other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts</i>	\$ -0-	\$ (368)	\$ (368)	\$ -0-
<i>Totals</i>	\$498,551	\$276,279 (73,271)	\$314,204 (12,683)	\$400,038

Report of Independent Accountants

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Coopers
& Lybrand

We have audited the accompanying balance sheet of Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the Council) as of June 30, 1992, and the related statements of revenue, expenses and changes in fund balance, cash flows and functional expenses for the year then ended. We previously audited and reported upon the financial statements of the Council for the year ended June 30, 1991, which condensed statements are included for comparative purposes only. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of Council on Library Resources, Inc. as of June 30, 1992, and the results of its operations and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles.

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads "Coopers & Lybrand".

Washington, D.C.
August 20, 1992

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1992

(with comparative totals for 1991)

	<u>1992</u>	<u>Totals 1991</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and cash equivalents (Note 2)	\$ 377,267	\$ 474,660
Investments (Note 2)	2,401,040	2,897,461
Grants receivable (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	600,000	—
Restricted	200,000	—
Other assets	<u>46,295</u>	<u>88,403</u>
Total assets	<u>\$3,624,602</u>	<u>\$3,460,524</u>
 LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 13,536	\$ 16,646
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	116,640	133,141
Restricted	283,398	365,410
Deferred revenue (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	900,000	300,000
Restricted	<u>337,852</u>	<u>244,095</u>
Total liabilities	1,651,426	1,059,292
Commitments (Note 6)		
Fund balance:		
Designated by Board of Directors (Note 2)	47,589	79,889
Undesignated	<u>1,925,587</u>	<u>2,321,343</u>
Total fund balance	<u>1,973,176</u>	<u>2,401,232</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$3,624,602</u>	<u>\$3,460,524</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

***Statement of Revenue, Expenses
and Changes in Fund Balance***

for the year ended June 30, 1992
(with comparative totals for 1991)

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Totals 1992	Totals 1991
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Revenue (Note 2):				
Grants and contracts	\$ 300,000	\$ 201,343	\$ 501,343	\$ 965,536
Interest	213,269	3,035	216,304	291,638
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total revenue	513,269	204,378	717,647	1,257,174
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 3, 5, 6 and 7):				
Program:				
Research	(202)	155,660	155,458	490,042
Human resources	148,517	15,307	163,824	375,872
Access and processing	153,606	413	154,019	177,955
Economics	89,143	30,499	119,642	—
Infrastructure	146,906	2,499	149,405	—
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total program expenses	537,970	204,378	742,348	1,043,869
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Administration	403,355	—	403,355	309,864
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total expenses	941,325	204,378	1,145,703	1,353,733
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses	(428,056)	—	(428,056)	(96,559)
Fund balance, beginning of year	2,401,232	—	2,401,232	2,497,791
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Fund balance, end of year	\$1,973,176	\$ —	\$1,973,176	\$2,401,232
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

Statement of Cash Flows

for the year ended June 30, 1992

(with comparative totals for 1991)

Cash flows from operating activities:
Excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses
Adjustments to reconcile excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses to net cash used in operating activities:
Amortization of investment (discounts) premiums
(Increase) decrease in grants receivable
Decrease in other assets
(Increase) decrease in deferred revenue
Decrease in accounts payable and accrued expenses
Decrease in grants and contracts payable
Total adjustments
Net cash used in operating activities
Cash flows from investing activities:
Purchase of investments
Sale of investments
Net cash provided by investing activities
Net decrease in cash and cash equivalents
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of the year
Cash and cash equivalents, end of the year

<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Totals 1992</u>	<u>Totals 1991</u>
\$ (428,056)	\$ —	\$ (428,056)	\$ (96,559)
415	—	415	1,311
(600,000)	(200,000)	(800,000)	709,900
42,108	—	42,108	6,126
600,000	93,757	693,757	(963,097)
(3,110)	—	(3,110)	(22,093)
(16,501)	(82,012)	(98,513)	(151,893)
<u>22,912</u>	<u>(188,255)</u>	<u>(165,343)</u>	<u>(419,746)</u>
<u>(405,144)</u>	<u>(188,255)</u>	<u>(593,399)</u>	<u>(516,305)</u>
(604,098)	(399,896)	(1,003,994)	(1,499,304)
<u>911,849</u>	<u>588,151</u>	<u>1,500,000</u>	<u>1,700,000</u>
<u>307,751</u>	<u>188,255</u>	<u>496,006</u>	<u>200,696</u>
(97,393)	—	(97,393)	(315,609)
<u>474,660</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>474,660</u>	<u>790,269</u>
<u>\$ 377,267</u>	<u>\$ —</u>	<u>\$ 377,267</u>	<u>\$ 474,660</u>

Statement of Functional Expenses

for the year ended June 30, 1992

(with comparative totals for 1991)

	Research	Human Resources	Access and Processing
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Unrestricted:			
Grants and contracts	\$ —	\$ 53,777	\$ 51,885
Refunds and overappropriations	(202)	(1,384)	(1,099)
Staff and travel	—	34,827	35,031
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	—	16,390	22,882
Board expenses	—	—	—
Support services including office expenses	—	44,907	44,907
	<u>(202)</u>	<u>148,517</u>	<u>153,606</u>
Restricted:			
Grants and contracts	122,242	—	—
Refunds and overappropriations	(67,372)	(3,214)	—
Staff and travel	9,414	—	—
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	16,832	17,977	413
Support services including office expenses	74,544	544	—
	<u>155,660</u>	<u>15,307</u>	<u>413</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$155,458</u>	<u>\$163,824</u>	<u>\$154,019</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

<u>Economics</u>	<u>Infrastructure</u>	<u>Total Program Expenses</u>	<u>Administration</u>	<u>Totals 1992</u>	<u>Totals 1991</u>
\$ —	\$ 21,375	\$127,037	\$ —	\$ 127,037	\$ 127,075
—	—	(2,685)	—	(2,685)	(67,843)
33,986	39,321	143,165	234,851	378,016	242,744
10,250	41,303	90,825	20,989	111,814	66,080
—	—	—	32,196	32,196	42,031
<u>44,907</u>	<u>44,907</u>	<u>179,628</u>	<u>115,319</u>	<u>294,947</u>	<u>278,110</u>
<u>89,143</u>	<u>146,906</u>	<u>537,970</u>	<u>403,355</u>	<u>941,325</u>	<u>688,197</u>
27,000	—	149,242	—	149,242	659,999
—	—	(70,586)	—	(70,586)	(221,096)
—	—	9,414	—	9,414	33,947
3,499	2,164	40,885	—	40,885	145,867
<u>—</u>	<u>335</u>	<u>75,423</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>75,423</u>	<u>46,819</u>
<u>30,499</u>	<u>2,499</u>	<u>204,378</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>204,378</u>	<u>665,536</u>
<u>\$119,642</u>	<u>\$149,405</u>	<u>\$742,348</u>	<u>\$403,355</u>	<u>\$1,145,703</u>	<u>\$1,353,733</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research.

The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

2. Summary of significant accounting policies

The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below:

Basis of accounting

The financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue

Grants to the Council are recorded in the balance sheet as grants receivable and as deferred grant revenues when awarded. Revenues of restricted grant funds are recognized only to the extent of expenditures that satisfy the restricted purposes of these grants.

Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized as income in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors.

Grants and contracts payable

Grants and contracts made by the Council are recorded in the balance sheet as grants and contracts payable and as an expense at the time recipients are awarded the grants. Current period expenses are reduced for grant or contract refunds or overappropriations when received.

Cash and cash equivalents, and investments

Cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market mutual fund. Investments which consist of treasury notes and treasury bills are recorded at amortized cost which approximates market. This balance includes restricted amounts of \$137,852 at June 30, 1992. Cash equivalents represent investments with original maturities of 90 days or less and, therefore, bear minimal risk. Interest which is not restricted by the related grants is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Board designated funds

In prior years, the Board of Directors had designated a portion of the fund balance for various short-term projects. During 1992, amounts totaling \$32,279 were transferred to the undesignated fund balance, representing a reduction in anticipated costs of the Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program and closure of other completed projects.

Reclassifications

In 1992, the Council redefined four of its five programs, Human resources, Access and processing, Economics, and Infrastructure and, accordingly, program expenses in the 1991 financial statements have been reclassified for comparative purposes.

3. Changes in restricted deferred revenue

	<u>1992</u>
Balance, beginning of year	\$244,095
Additions:	
Grants	<u>300,000</u>
	544,095
Deductions, funds expended or refunded during the year:	
Grants	<u>206,243</u>
Balance, end of year	<u>\$337,852</u>

4. Income taxes

The Council, a private operating foundation, is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3) and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

5. Retirement plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program (the Plan) administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the

Council's contributions. The Council's contribution, net of that reimbursed by the Commission on Preservation and Access (the Commission), was approximately \$53,100 in fiscal year 1992.

6. *Commitments*

The Council has entered into a noncancelable lease agreement for office space which expires in May 1993. The minimum future rental due will be approximately \$158,000 through May 1993. As part of this lease agreement, the Council will be assessed an annual charge based on its proportionate share of the increase in the operating costs of the building. For the year ended June 30, 1992, rent expense totaled \$137,500, of which approximately \$4,100 represents the Council's share of the increase in the operating costs.

The Council subleases a portion of its leased office space. Rental income from this sublease amounted to approximately \$42,000 in fiscal year 1992.

7. *Commission on Preservation and Access*

The Commission on Preservation and Access (the Commission) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information. In 1989, the Council granted to the Commission \$2,067,000 it had received on behalf of the Commission for support of the Commission's preservation program. Also, in 1989, the Council awarded to the Commission a general support grant totaling \$200,000, all of which had been paid at June 30, 1992.

The Council also entered into an agreement with the Commission effective July 1, 1988 through December 31, 1991 under which the Council provided office space, employee services including employee benefits, equipment, supplies and other overhead items to the Commission. Commission staff members were employees of the Council and received the same benefits as staff members of the Council. A percentage of shared overhead costs which was negotiated annually was charged to the Commission. For fiscal year 1992, the Commission's share was 25%. The total amount of direct expenses of \$154,570 and other overhead costs of \$43,100 were charged to the Commission for fiscal year 1992.

Certain members of the Council's Board of Directors are also members of the Commission's Board of Directors. However, as these members are in the minority and there are no other elements of managerial or financial control, these two entities have not been combined.

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